

Received 27 June 2024, accepted 7 August 2024, date of publication 11 September 2024, date of current version 27 December 2024.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3457885

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Virtual Reality Critical Thinking Training of Engineers in the Vertical Transportation Industry

YAVAR JARRAH-NEZHAD¹, LUIS A. PAIPA-GALEANO², CÉSAR A. BERNAL-TORRES³,
WILMER GARZÓN-ALFONSO¹, YAMID DELGHANS-JACOME²,
AND ANDRES FELIPE PÁEZ-CAICEDO^{3,4}

¹Escuela Colombiana de Ingeniería Julio Garavito, Bogotá 111166, Colombia

²Faculty of Engineering, Universidad de La Sabana, Chía 111321, Colombia

³International School of Economic and Administrative Sciences, Universidad de La Sabana, Chía 111321, Colombia

⁴Fogafín, Bogotá 110311, Colombia

Corresponding author: Yavar Jarrah-Nezhad (yavar.jarrah@escuelaing.edu.co)

This work involved human subjects in its research. Approval of all ethical and experiential procedures and protocols was granted by the Universidad de la Sabana.

ABSTRACT Concerns have emerged regarding the expenses associated with integrating virtual reality into the digital transformation of companies, stemming from costs related to 3D software development and procurement of headsets. Despite the acknowledged benefits of experiential learning in military training, education and medicine, industrial adoption of virtual reality remains constrained. This study delves into the distinctive advantages of virtual reality in the elevator industry and proposes a cost-effective and innovative virtual reality (VR) training solution and evaluation model aimed at improving the learning outcomes of engineers in the field, grounded in the critical thinking theory. The proposed model seeks to capitalize on the benefits of VR in projects geared towards digital transformation by identifying “meta-requirements” and “principal designs” through a design science research method focused on problem solving. This approach has potential applications in other domains. Our methodology employs a unique strategy to develop a virtual reality experiential training program that harnesses engineers’ cognitive potential to enhance their critical thinking skills. To evaluate the effectiveness of this approach, we conducted a comparative analysis with a control group trained through traditional digital methods, concentrating on “decision-making and problem-solving” as well as “thinking through hypothesis testing.” Engineers undergoing virtual reality training exhibited heightened motivation, emotional engagement, and curiosity levels toward the subject, providing detailed accounts of their experiential training in relation to physical space and time. The “learning by doing” approach resulted in a 15% enhancement in critical thinking among participants, along with a notable 44% improvement in recognition memory.

INDEX TERMS Decision making, digital transformation, Halpern critical thinking, industrial application, problem solving, strategic information system management, training engineers, virtual reality.

I. INTRODUCTION

Companies actively seek innovative approaches to enhance their value chains, provide training to their staff, and drive digital transformation strategies. According to a survey conducted among top managers by the World Economic Forum (WEF), critical thinking (CT) and problem-solving skills are anticipated to be highly valued by employers by 2025.

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Christian Esposito.

Currently, companies estimate that on average, 40% of their workforce will require reskilling. The survey of managers underscores the urgent need to expedite digitalization efforts and prioritize skill enhancement and reskilling [1].

VR training plays a crucial role in bridging the gap between Industry 4.0 and human-technology interaction (Industry 5.0), an area that still lacks comprehensive research. Concurrently, research indicates a significant surge in interest in VR in college education and learning contexts as a transformative tool for innovation in education [2]. In the

realm of VR applications, the International Data Corporation (IDC) has documented a consistent increase in investment in Extended reality (XR) which refers to augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and mixed reality over the past five years since 2018. This growth, assessed at 78.5% between 2018 and 2019, was anticipated to maintain a five-year Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 77.0%. However, this upward trajectory tapered off, resulting in a much slower growth rate (39.5% CAGR). The subdued state of the market is not unexpected given the economic downturn and the limited number of suppliers for both AR and VR headsets. Significant transformations have transpired in recent years, with standalone headsets demonstrating a noteworthy CAGR of 57.5%, while screenless viewers such as Samsung's Gear VR have essentially vanished from the market. According to IDC's latest findings of the IDC, this downward pattern persists, evident in the global decline of AR/VR headset shipments plummeting by 44.6% annually in 2023. The IDC anticipates a market resurgence in 2024, with a robust year-over-year growth of 46.8%. This revival was attributed to the introduction of new hardware by Meta and ByteDance, the launch of Apple's Vision Pro, and the increasing influence of smaller companies. By 2027, the global market is forecast to reach 30.3 million units [3].

The role of VR in the digital transformation of companies has raised concerns about its high cost, attributed to expenses related to 3D software development and acquiring headsets, as well as optimizing the return on investment. While the proven benefits of experiential learning in contexts such as military training, education and medicine have been recognized in practice, the industrial adoption of VR has been limited.

Even today, numerous companies continue to rely on conventional methods for engineering training, neglecting the potential advantages of XR technology to meet their strategic and performance objectives. While previous research has explored digital transformation, particularly in VR training across various disciplines, such as education, strategic management, planning, design, and development, there remains a gap in addressing tangible industry challenges that require CT. Existing studies are predominantly theoretical, analyzing digital transformation or training through VR or CT in isolation. These investigations failed to assess the impact of VR training on CT compared to traditional and digital education methods in an industrial context. Finally, there is a void in both theoretical and practical research concerning the design of digital transformation solutions for VR training among engineers in the industry, specifically focusing on the skills necessary for comprehending complex real-world issues using problem-solving and CT abilities.

The problem of this research revolves around an elevator company's need to consult with clients to prepare a contract tailored to the personalized design and implementation of elevators. In this initial phase, it is crucial for engineers and technical staff to present an optimal solution

considering various factors, such as engineering specifications, human experience, and situational requirements. Subsequently, in the operational phase, engineers and technical staff collaborate to deliver and install finished products. Quick decision-making and recommendations from the engineering team are paramount for meeting deadlines, ensuring quality control, and achieving customer satisfaction. Mistakes at this stage can be expensive and may result in delays that affect customer satisfaction.

Conventional practice in the elevator industry involves inviting domain experts to conduct approximately two-week training courses for the staff. These courses include lectures, workshops, and the use of electronic educational materials, such as videos or specially designed training applications for elevator-related calculations. The experts provide trainees with a theoretical book and study materials. Following this training period, evaluations assess the trainees' knowledge. However, this method has several limitations. Experts often need to travel long distances, which incurs significant costs for tickets and accommodation. Additionally, the short duration of training makes it challenging to ensure that the material is retained in the long-term memory of the trainees. There are no follow-up sessions, that leads to forgetting important details.

Additionally, engineers in this industry encounter unique, diverse, and complex problems that require immediate attention. In such scenarios, CT plays a pivotal role in understanding the situation and in making decisions based on a broad range of solutions or combinations of options. Engineers must possess a profound understanding of the subject matter and the ability to develop innovative solutions to effectively address these challenges.

We investigated the unique benefits of integrating VR into the industrial sector and propose an economical and creative VR training solution and assessment model. Our goal is to enhance the learning outcomes of engineers grounded in CT theory, with the potential for broader applications across diverse domains. This assessment is a valuable tool for evaluating the feasibility of incorporating this technology into digital transformation initiatives, especially in developing markets with limited financial resources. We employed an innovative approach to develop a VR experiential training program utilizing a design science research method focused on problem solving. This study identifies "meta-requirements" and "principal designs" by leveraging engineers' cognitive potential to improve CT skills. To assess its effectiveness, we compare the results with a control group using traditional digital methods, focusing on "decision-making," "problem-solving," and "hypothesis testing."

The main question of this paper is: How can we design, plan, implement, and evaluate CT training for engineers in the vertical transportation industry by applying virtual reality as a digital transformation solution?

Specifically, we also explore the following questions:

- In which aspects can VR training in the industry add value to engineers' CT enhancement?

- How can we empirically demonstrate that VR training increases engineers' skills in CT?

- How to plan, design, and implement a VR software and hardware solution to improve CT skills and compare it with traditional training implementation?

Initially, we conducted a literature review examining the assessment and evaluation methods applied to engineering training, along with an exploration of the role of VR and the approaches used in solution development. Subsequently, we identified the gaps within the subject area. The Methodology section outlines the process of creating an innovative solution designed to enhance training outcomes in VR.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II delves into previous research and elucidates how our study extends upon it. Section III outlines the methodology used in our study. In Section IV, we present and discuss the results. Finally, Section V presents our conclusions and outlines avenues for future research.

II. RELATED WORK

Efforts were made to present the advantages of VR applications within the industry, including training employees engaged in production tasks in a smart factory. This initiative led to a reduction in the time required to complete production tasks and a decrease in the number of non-compliant products under real conditions [4]. A literature review of Simulation in industry 4.0 shows different approaches to decision making as well as the design and operations of complex and smart production systems that aid companies to evaluate the risks, costs, implementation barriers, impact on operational performance, and roadmap toward Industry 4.0 [5]. However, a perspective on designing systems that can prove to be beneficial in terms of securing critical thinking particularly in VR training are lacking. An exploration of Simulation in Industry 4.0 through literature review reveals various methodologies for decision-making, design, and operations of intricate and intelligent production systems. These approaches assist companies in assessing risks, costs, implementation obstacles, impact on operational performance, and the path toward Industry 4.0 [5]. Nevertheless, there exists a gap in the perspective concerning the design of systems that can be advantageous, specifically in terms of promoting critical thinking, particularly in VR training. Additionally, evaluation methods ensuring results that contribute to the adoption of VR technology are absent. Our focus is on CT theory and its application to training engineers within the vertical transportation industry using VR. We examined the assessment and evaluation techniques for gauging the effectiveness of VR training, examined CT theory, and ultimately elucidated the rationale for guiding the design approaches in VR software and hardware development.

A. ASSESSMENT AND EVALUATION METHODS

Historically, training evaluation has primarily concentrated on discerning immediate participant reactions to the overall training and assessing the participant's learning level upon

completing the training. However, over the past decade, organizational demands for increased accountability have redirected attention towards measuring returns on investment [6]. Recent technological progress has influenced both the administration of training (virtual and simulated) and assessment of training (biometrics and analytics).

Quantitative measures have been used to assess the user's physical state, encompassing techniques such as eye tracking for specifying eye fixation and duration, facial expression analysis to gauge micro expressions or muscle activities indicating the user's emotions during the experiment, galvanic skin response reflecting skin conductance, and heart rate variability. The measurement of these factors involves acquiring dedicated sensors and developing software to extract and analyze the data [7]. Qualitative evaluation, which has interpretivism, epistemological orientation, and constructionism as its main ontological orientation, describes complex phenomena [7]. In VR training, qualitative research aids in comprehending an individual's experiences associated with a particular phenomenon. This comprehension is crucial for facilitating and enhancing the "transfer of training," a pivotal aspect as organizations equip their workforce with the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities essential for executing diverse job activities [8]. Transfer of training refers to the ability of learners to apply the knowledge and skills acquired during a training session to their respective job roles. The notion of transferring either learning or training is an ongoing subject of study and discussion, posing challenges for organizations to pinpoint the specific critical factors that should be considered when addressing this topic. According to Grossman and Salas [9], the transfer of training is closely related to elements such as trainee characteristics (cognitive ability, self-efficacy, motivation, and perceived utility of training), training design (behavioral modeling, error management, and realistic training environments), and work environment (transfer climate, support, opportunity to perform, and follow-up). In virtual environments, the challenge of the transfer of training is context or situated learning, which is the difference between VR training and its real-world application. It is important to concentrate on the design stage to embed all critical knowledge that should be part of the training outcomes [10]. Negative transfer occurs when the training result obstructs real-world performance or causes confusion for the employee rather than aiding in improvement. This phenomenon occurs in VR-based training when the virtual environment is ineffective in simulating and accurately reflecting real-world tasks [11]. In precision-dependent tasks, such as surgery, haptic feedback plays a crucial role in ensuring that the outcomes of operations align with expectations [12], [13].

Despite its limitations, VR significantly influences training by providing the opportunity for experiential learning, resulting in a noteworthy learning retention rate of 75% compared to the 20% retention rate associated with audio-visual methods. In addition, it provides learners with the capability to engage in all their senses, facilitating the potential for

repetition in scenarios characterized by high budgets, risks, or similar variations in input scenarios [14].

By leveraging cognitive psychology, VR harnesses the principles of experiential learning and emphasizes learning through direct experiences. These immersive experiences aid comprehension and memory retention by establishing associations between the different senses. The foundation of this approach lies in experiential learning theory, introduced by psychologist David Kolb in 1984. Subsequently, scholars, such as John Dewey, Kurt Lewin, and Jean Piaget, further advanced this theory [15]. According to this theory, adults learn most effectively through hands-on experiences rather than through passive methods, such as listening or reading. Experiential learning theory underscores the significance of adult learning by engaging with their experiences and deriving meaning from them rather than relying on rote memorization [16]. Experiential learning theory comprises four stages: concrete learning, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. The first two stages of the cycle involve comprehending an experience, while the subsequent two stages concentrate on transforming an experience. Kolb contended that learning is most effective when the learner completes the entire loop [15], [16].

Early efforts to integrate technology into experiential learning involved assigning group tasks, such as decision-making problems, and training them through a diverse array of methods, including simulations, cases, games, observation tools, role plays, and skill practice routines. These approaches yielded superior results compared with non-experiential learning groups. The common principle underlying these technologies is the creation of simulated situations designed to provide learners with personal experiences that prompt inquiry and facilitate their understanding process [17].

We applied self-reported participant reflection as a qualitative method, administered in a written form. This approach allowed participants to delve more profoundly into their training experiences through probing. Reflection seeks insights into how the training experience impacted the participant, the new perspectives it generated, and how the participant anticipates feeling or behaving differently after the training. In essence, the self-reported reflection method not only serves as a means of evaluating VR-based simulations but also offers participants an additional opportunity for learning. We avoided the haptic feedback problem using a simulation learning method that eliminated inaccuracies in the input devices.

The existing literature lacks consensus on delineating the learning outcomes and design principles essential for attaining understanding. In engineering, numerous knowledge domains rely on contextual comprehension of topics, with no established guidelines for achieving conclusive results. For instance, in elevator engineering, professionals must cultivate an intuitive understanding of how elevators function and the variances introduced by altering parameters such as motor types, door or window configurations, cabin dimensions,

the number of elevators on each floor, or varying distances and waiting conditions. Therefore, acquiring knowledge and comprehending various situations necessitate exposure to diverse configurations through multiple iterations, complemented by a theoretical understanding to refine performance indicators. The CT theory discussed in Subsection B can offer a solution to this issue.

To acknowledge the advantages of VR, managers must understand the imperative of grasping the challenges and benefits associated with digital transformation through VR training, enabling them to make informed decisions.

B. CRITICAL THINKING

Critical thinking (CT) holds significant importance across various domains. For instance, it serves as a crucial tool for medical students to navigate ill-defined medical emergencies, enabling them to exercise sound judgment in clinical situations and effectively address clinical problems. CT is widely recognized as a fundamental competency that should be nurtured and evaluated within every medical school curriculum. Methods and Instruments for Enhancing and Evaluating the Critical Thinking Abilities of Medical Students encompass Problem-based learning, Case-based learning, Think, pair, and share approach, Flipped classroom instruction, Reflective writing, and Script concordance test [18]. An example of CT in military is the concept of red team that offers commanders an autonomous capability to thoroughly examine alternatives in plans, operations, concepts, organizations, and capabilities within the operational environment, considering viewpoints from partners, adversaries, and other stakeholders. A Red Team undertakes three primary types of tasks which are providing support to operations, planning, and decision-making processes; conducting critical review and analysis of pre-existing plans; and offering intelligence support through threat emulation. In complex and stressful situations, military leaders are tasked with making tactical decisions amidst incomplete and uncertain knowledge. Information given to battle commanders is frequently incomplete, potentially inaccurate, and occasionally intentionally deceptive. In such scenarios, the application of critical thinking skills to assess battlefield information becomes paramount [19]. In general, given the rapid pace of change, many individuals alive today will find themselves in jobs that do not currently exist, while the abundance of information renders today's knowledge quickly obsolete. Consequently, two primary goals for education emerge: learning how to continuously learn and developing critical thinking skills to navigate rapidly changing information landscapes. We confront numerous new challenges including environmental issues, dilemmas surrounding weapons of mass destruction, political disputes over resource distribution, mental health concerns, increasing violence, and an aging population. These global challenges strain resources and jeopardize life on earth. To address these pressing issues effectively, a well-educated and critically thinking populace is indispensable [20].

Solving engineering problems typically demands an analytical perspective and abstract comprehension of the intricate components within multidimensional systems. It often relies on structured and logical thought processes involving assessment, interpretation, and judgment. Development of CT skills is important in this context [21].

Engineering problems share common characteristics with the concept of wicked problems introduced by Rittel and Weber [22]. These wicked problems exhibit the following traits: uniqueness in each situation, absence of a clear problem definition, multicausality, multiscalarly and interconnectedness, involvement of multiple stakeholders with conflicting agendas, straddling of organizational and disciplinary boundaries, ramifications of every solution throughout the system, evaluation of solutions not as right or wrong but as better or worse, extended time required for solution assessment, and problems that are never completely solved. Likewise, engineering problems face challenges, such as conflicting interests and goals, diverse solution methods, engineering and non-engineering constraints, collaborative systems with distributed knowledge sharing, and polymorphic problem representation. Moreover, as highlighted by Lönngren and Svanström [23], engineers encounter difficulties when dealing with wicked sustainability problems owing to constant changes, high complexity, uncertainty, and value conflicts [21], [24].

Ensuring that engineers acquire the skills to tackle intricate problems poses a challenge, and assessing university engineering programs is a routine task for accreditation bodies such as the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET). Universities following ABET instructions use concepts such as learning outcomes to measure the efficiency of the training process in higher education. According to Clovis Community College, Learning Outcomes refer to quantifiable statements that articulate, from the outset, what students are expected to comprehend, achieve, or value upon completing a course or program (also known as backward course design). These outcomes serve as effective and valuable tools for enhancing student success by assessing the genuine acquisition of knowledge and skills imparted by courses, programs, services, and institutions [25]. Despite the significant role that CT plays in addressing engineering training challenges, previous research has predominantly focused on pedagogical approaches, decision-making processes, and experimental accomplishments. The emphasis is typically on analytical skills, inference, explanation, evaluation, interpretation, curiosity, and analyticity. The development of CT involves articulating assumptions for specific problems, selecting suitable hypotheses and experimental methods, and structuring open-design problems [26]. In practice, applying and integrating CT into engineering training fall into three categories: infusive (incorporating thinking skills into the instructional process), immersive (utilizing digital education to address issues of student interest and engagement), and mixed approaches. Universities usually apply two evaluation

and intervention durations during one semester. For instance, ABET assesses the skills in each semester through feedback loops (assessment, revision, and implementation). The study also highlighted problem-solving/problem-based learning, case-based studies, and lecture discussions as the most applied training strategies. These strategies underscore the importance of teaching engineering skills in a manner that directly relates to real workplace problems.

According to ABET, engineering programs equip graduates with a set of at least seven learning outcomes, each related to various aspects of CT development [27]: (1) Demonstrating the capability to identify, formulate, and solve intricate engineering problems by applying the principles of engineering, science, and mathematics. 2) Applying engineering design to generate solutions that address specified needs while considering factors such as public health, safety, welfare, and global, cultural, social, environmental, and economic considerations. 3) Effective communication with diverse audience members 4) Recognizing ethical and professional responsibilities in engineering situations and making informed judgments that consider the broader impact of engineering solutions in global, economic, environmental, and societal contexts. 5) Effective functioning within a team, exhibiting leadership, fostering a collaborative and inclusive environment, establishing goals, planning tasks, and achieving objectives. 6) Developing and conducting appropriate experimentation, analyzing, and interpreting data, and employing engineering judgment to draw conclusions. 7) Acquire and apply new knowledge as necessary, utilizing appropriate learning strategies.

Learning outcome statements must include words that reflect critical or higher order thinking to demonstrate that students are learning valuable skills. According to Bloom's taxonomy, a high level of thinking ability can be measured in terms of knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, evaluation, and synthesis.

Quantitative and qualitative methodologies serve as tools to assess CT skills. Each method involves a testing approach that is constrained when evaluating multiple individuals simultaneously. For larger groups, researchers employ multiple selection tests with closed questions, whereas small groups often utilize open-ended questions or essays. Closed-ended questions generally exhibit acceptable reliability, but only assess predetermined aspects, posing challenges for repeatability. Conversely, open-ended questions or essays are adaptable to specific needs and are easier to replicate but have limited reliability. Researchers have attempted to create hybrid proposals that incorporate both types of questions, exemplified by the Halpern CT Skills Test and CT Testing (MEC Paraguay). There are closed-question tests such as the Watson-Glaser CT Assessment, California CT Skills Test, California CT disposition inventory, and the Cornell CT Test. Examples of open-ended questionnaires include the CT Salamanca, and CT Tasks [28]. Based on the prior study, our research applies the Halpern CT Test as an assessment tool

because of its higher statistical reliability of 0.88-0.77 on Cronbach's alpha.

C. VR HEAD MOUNTED DEVICE

According to the literature, VR systems are divided into the following categories: training drills (i.e., treatment of psychological illnesses and anxiety disorders, therapy games for stroke survivors, forensic psychiatry, and medical education of students, drills in the army), planning design (heritage projects, archaeology, tourism, and digital museums), and presentation entertainment (i.e., imaginative games and virtual driving simulation) [29].

Research focusing on the success of VR products in terms of their usability underscores that achieving comprehensive VR production is currently hindered by numerous challenges, including non-standardized Head-Mounted Displays (HMDs), issues of usability, accessibility concerns, lack of guidelines, and challenges in the evaluation process. In this context, usability refers to the ease of use of a product, with ease of service being a measurable attribute. Insights from industrial practitioners reveal several observations: a notable distinction between traditional software development and VR development due to complexity, lack of structure and formulation based on varying participation levels, absence of comprehensive testing procedures to enhance multiple product releases, the expensive nature of personalized evaluation, the time and cost involved in versioning and maintenance, and the paramount importance of Quality of Experience in VR products [30].

An examination of the literature on the integration of virtual reality (VR) in education highlights the significant challenges posed by high acquisition costs and usability concerns, which stand out as primary impediments to the widespread adoption of this technology [31]. In general, the insufficient technological performance of these headsets, high costs, and the need for a greater variety of applications are factors hindering the widespread adoption and success of this technology [32]. For example, Statista estimated that the VR headset average price worldwide per unit amounts to 419.92 U.S. dollars in 2028 [33], which does not show signs of reduction. In addition to financial and design challenges, prior research contends that users may encounter symptoms of motion sickness or cybersickness due to hardware, display type and mode, hardware field-of-view, latency, and flicker. These symptoms include but are not limited to eye fatigue, disorientation, and nausea, all of which have the potential to impede the VR experience for users [34], [35]. Attempts have been made to reduce this effect by surveying the subjects and measuring their sickness responses [36].

For the design of our HMDs, we consider the points from the literature and use a multi-criteria decision-making methodology "The Analytic Hierarchy Process" (AHP) to identify the VR HMD compatible with criteria such as acquisition ease in Colombia, low price, biosafety of the headsets for multiple use, usability, ergonomics, quality of use and the input data.

In the realm of design within service systems engineering, the widely accepted methodology for developing and assessing the performance of artifacts is Design Science Research (DSR) and the approach adopted for our research. DSR represents a contemporary research approach. Its primary objective is not to elucidate an existing reality or contribute to its comprehension but rather to construct a new reality by addressing problems. This methodology consists of a cyclical process that involves expert interviews and an analysis process to identify problems and opportunities and define meta-requirements. It then applies design principles and undergoes system evaluation (see Fig. 1), ultimately resulting in the definition of key variables for the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) of VR software [37], [38].

FIGURE 1. Design Science Research for VR software development.

III. METHODS AND TOOLS

The primary objective of this study is to formulate, plan, execute, and assess CT training programs tailored for engineers in the vertical transportation industry, utilizing virtual reality as a solution for digital transformation. Achieving this objective requires evaluating the requirements for designing HMDs and developing a full-stack software design for mobile phones to deliver VR training to assure internal validity. Internal validity pertains to the assurance level that the causal relationship under examination is dependable and unaffected by external factors or variables. In addition, the design involves the collection and storage of information in the cloud and the creation of a traditional training solution without VR. The design must adhere to best practices to ensure the development of VR HMDs that positively affect the training of engineers in the elevator industry, particularly in terms of CT. A comparison between VR training and traditional training was facilitated by designing two identical training experiences, except for the VR training component, which was replaced with traditional digital audio-visual training in the control group. VR training occurs in a digital virtual environment, necessitating a thorough understanding of the associated technical challenges. Our research methodology was divided into four distinct areas, each presenting unique challenges, as outlined in Table 1, in response to the design requirements.

In this study, 254 engineering students from the "Universidad de la Sabana" along with 100 technical staff from a reputable elevating company in Colombia participated. The selection criteria for the samples required that

individuals be either practicing engineers or enrolled in the final semesters of a mechanical or industrial engineering program with little or no knowledge of the subject area. Additionally, participants must have access to a cell phone, a computer and suitable space to carry out the assigned tasks. The participants were randomly assigned to two equal-sized groups, one for traditional training and the other for VR training, with a modified Halpern test used for CT evaluation.

TABLE 1. Method challenge per area.

Research planning and design	VR Head Mounted Display	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection type • Requirements • (MVP)
	VR Software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meta-requirements • Development engine • Game development
Critical thinking evaluation	Critical Thinking test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection type • Measured variables • Adaptation specific test
	Measuring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability

The methodology for each domain provides a set of steps essential for crafting a corresponding specialized procedure, focusing either on the hardware or HMDs design, software intricacies (see Fig. 1), and adaptations to the Halpern CT test tailored specifically for the VR experiment (see Fig. 2). Subsection A on the VR HMD elaborates on the design of the requisite hardware specifications using the AHP method, along with outlining a prototype process utilized to create the MVP. The conceptual design of VR software is determined through design science research, where meta-requirements are identified, and a feedback loop assesses the design process in subsection B. For the evaluation of CT, variables are defined, the test type is selected, and it is customized (see subsection C. critical thinking evaluation). In addition, a training schedule was established. Finally, enriching the understanding of the quality of use was gained by open-ended questions gauging the usability of VR-based training in the context of digital transformation.

FIGURE 2. Methodology design.

A. VR HEAD MOUNTED DEVICE

The research utilizes AHP, a multi-criteria decision-making methodology, to identify a VR HMD that aligns with reusability concerns and biosecurity requirements, especially in cases such as COVID. The criteria encompass various considerations, such as price, usability, availability in Colombia, ergonomics, reusability, biosafety, and input data processing difficulty. The score of the VR HMD by criteria illustrates the rating of VR HMD alternatives and the weight assigned to each criterion (see Fig. 3). The proposed HMDs are well received in the market and exhibit visual characteristics based on the current hardware taxonomy for output devices (see Fig. 3). Ultimately, based on the results of the AHP method for selecting the VR HMD, Google Cardboard meets the design requirements for MVP.

	Weight	1	2	3	4	5
Biosafety	Desinfection time	20%	SAMSUNG oculus Inconvenient HTC			Google →
	Risk to Transfer by contact	20%	Inconvenient ←		SAMSUNG oculus HTC	Google → Convenient
Price		20%	HTC oculus Inconvenient ←			Google → Convenient
		20%	Difficult ←		Google	SAMSUNG oculus HTC Easy
Acquisition in Colombia	10%	Difficult ←			Google SAMSUNG oculus	HTC → Easy
Ergonomic	5%	Unergonomic ←		Google		SAMSUNG oculus HTC Ergonomic
Input data	5%	Difficult ←		Google		SAMSUNG oculus HTC Easy

FIGURE 3. The score of VR HMD by criteria.

It costs US\$15, falling within the lowest price range for HMDs, and is a candidate that can be reused without incurring high costs for bio-safety measures. We deployed a reverse engineering process to study the construction of Google Cardboard based on Google’s instruction reference I/O 2015 for Cardboard [39] to create the new VR HMD (see Fig. 4). The reference guide does not discuss the reasons behind the choices they made and the use cases. They are manufacturing guides with practical schemes for 3D printing for general use or particularly for the VR applications made by their purposely made platform which is not necessarily industrial. Our reverse engineering approach is not only about recreating the parts exactly as they are made but also about understanding the design choices, implications, intricacies, and improvements in terms of design and materials necessary for our use case. We adopted a structure outlining the main characteristics of the MVP design process from Google’s guidelines (Google, 2015). Following the deconstruction of Google Cardboard specifications, we concentrated on examining alternative materials, lenses, mechanical design, and the manufacturing process.

We tested various cardboard materials (see Tables 2 and 3) and chose corrugated cardboard (E-flute type) with a thickness of 1.7 mm based on Google Cardboard criteria. We also tested numerous lens alternatives ranging from handcrafted constructions using PET bottles and water to magnifying glasses with different diameters. The lenses approved by

FIGURE 4. Google cardboard structure.

Google do not meet our criteria because of their higher prices, prompting us to opt for magnifying glasses with a 30 mm diameter, which is the same size recommended in the original Google design. In terms of mechanical design, utilizing the instructions and templates from Google Cardboard empowered us to create an MVP. This involved eliminating unnecessary features from the VR HMD, resulting in reduced raw material usage and shortened manufacturing time.

TABLE 2. Cardboard material alternatives.

Sample	Characteristics	Advantage	Disadvantages
No. 1	Corrugated cardboard [double face C-flute] Thickness: 4mm	- Low cost - Easy access - High resistance in bending	- Difficult handle - Very heavy - Long cutting time
No. 2	Corrugated cardboard [double face E-flute] Thickness: 1.7mm	- Easy handle - High resistance in bending - Shortcutting time	- High cost - Difficult access
No. 3	Corrugated cardboard [single face] Thickness: 2mm	- Low cost - Easy access - Shortcutting time	- Very unstable - Low resistance in bending
No. 4	Greyboard Thickness: 2mm	- Easy handle - Easy access	- Long cutting time - Low resistance in bending

In Autodesk AutoCAD the new design created shows the structure of this model (excluding lenses), featuring three main components: the case structure, lens frame, and visual division (see Fig. 5 and 6).

The new design has greater depth, and the inside walls are painted matte black to avoid any reflections inside the HMD. There is a band for balancing cell phone weight and providing a comfortable experience while moving the head. Our primary contribution lies in the innovative approach and methodology for integrating critical thinking into VR software design. This integration is precisely designed to

TABLE 3. Lenses alternatives.

Sample	Characteristics	Advantage	Disadvantages
No. 1	Two caps of PET circles with water inside to get the refraction effect.	- Low cost - Easy access	- Blurred focus - Difficult construction - Risk of wetness - Difficult handle - Deviation from original Google design
No. 2	Two caps of acetate circles with water inside to get the refraction effect.	- Low cost - Easy access	- Blurred focus - Difficult construction - Risk of wetness - Difficult handle - Deviation from original Google design
No. 3	Small plastic bag with lock zip with water inside to get the refraction effect.	- Low cost - Easy access	- Blurred focus - Difficult construction - Risk of wetness - Difficult handle - Deviation from original Google design
No. 4	Magnifying glass Diameter: 30mm	- Acceptable focus - Easy handle	- High cost - Deviation from original Google design
No. 5	Magnifying glass Diameter: 40mm	- Acceptable focus - Easy handle	- Distraction by lighting - High cost - Deviation from original Google design
No. 6	Magnifying glass Diameter: 50mm	- Acceptable focus - Easy handle	- Distraction by lighting - High cost - Deviation from original Google design

FIGURE 5. Adjustment of focus distance.

generate superior outcomes in terms of overall experience, training effectiveness, and final results. It enhances participants' decision-making abilities derived from critical thinking and understanding of the problem, providing a heightened perception of the situation, and a more profound grasp of time and space. The examination of the VR experience's quality ensures that the modifications positively influence learning. The final design costs approximately \$4 to produce in Colombia (see Fig. 7 and 8). This affordability is particularly plausible considering that a typical commercial VR headset has an average price of approximately US \$390, whereas Google Cardboard is priced at around US \$15.

FIGURE 6. Comparison Google Cardboard and new design.

This difference is significant if a company decides to train a considerable number of employees. For instance, acquisition of 100 headsets for training in a country like Colombia, where over 80% of companies are small or medium-sized is considered feasible.

FIGURE 7. Assembly process.

FIGURE 8. New VR HMD.

B. VR SOFTWARE

We adopted DSR, the established approach for the creation and functionality of artifacts, serving as the foundation for the development of VR software.

The analysis was initiated with interviews with two experts in the elevator industry to identify the critical factors influencing elevator configuration. During these discussions, emphasis was placed on factors such as the end of the working day and the presence of clients around elevators. Experts highlighted that effective traffic management plays a crucial role in securing projects and maintaining brand reputation, particularly in office building environments. The experts indicated that a notable challenge among the responsible actors is the time-consuming process of understanding customer requirements and predicting traffic scenarios without the aid of traffic calculation software. The expert interviews revealed existing issues and opportunities within the training process, revealing that trainers, predominantly engineers, lack pedagogical skills and impact communication effectiveness.

While there is a global consensus on vertical transportation traffic theory, variations exist in evaluation criteria and regional regulations. Training processes also differ among companies and are often treated as confidential matters. Consequently, this study focused on the analysis of a typical training process. Engineers receive infrequent magisterial class training a few times a year, and each engineer is individually responsible for skill improvement thereafter. Another issue is that the training materials primarily consist of images and written tasks that lack visual training tools.

After the interviews, the results identified opportunities that can be categorized into seven Meta-Requirements (MRs):

MR-1: Incorporating the building's spatial environment: A VR-based training system should integrate the spatial environment of an office building.

MR-2: People Movements (from the hall to the elevator): The VR-based training system should accurately represent people's movements in the lobby and their entry and exit from the elevator.

MR-3: Elevator configuration (size and quantity): The VR-based training system should depict modifications to the elevator size and quantity, illustrating the impact of each arrangement on individuals within the cabin.

MR-4: Realistic experience: The VR-based training system must strive for realism to enhance the learning process and provide knowledge that is applicable to real-world scenarios.

MR-5: Intuitiveness: The VR-based training system should have a user-friendly interface that allows trainees to interact without prior training.

MR-6: Visual impact of the input data: The VR-based training system should visually convey changes in the input data, such as door type, size, and loading ratio.

MR-7: Suggest the starting point of the simulation. The VR-based training system should recommend a starting point to ensure a positive experience and minimize complications at the beginning of the simulation.

The implementation in 3D application applies the MRs (see Fig. 9, 10, and 12).

FIGURE 9. Presentation of the main floor in Unity 3D interface.

FIGURE 10. Camera's mode experience from the VR mode.

These meta-requirements give rise to Design Principles (DPs) that guide the development of the training system (see Fig. 11 and 12):

DP-1: Use of existing theory: Leveraging existing knowledge about vertical transportation traffic allows for minor adaptations, aligning with MR-2.

DP-2: Simple interface: This design principle emphasizes a straightforward and intuitive interface that is essential for interaction without prior training (MR-5). Additionally, suggesting a starting point (MR-7) minimized unpleasant experiences for inexperienced trainees.

DP-3: Precise imitation of reality in designing elevator parts: Given the diverse scenarios in each simulation, accurately replicating the elevator configurations is crucial. Interaction is the key to understanding and learning, aligning with MR-1, MR-3, MR-4, and MR-6.

We created a virtual reality office building environment capable of accommodating eight elevators and a maximum of ten floors, offering both first-person and third-person camera perspectives. The VR experience was developed using the 3D Studio Max software to construct 3D objects, while images of materials were crafted using Adobe Photoshop. The simulation was conducted in a virtual environment

FIGURE 11. The input and output forms.

built using the Unity Game 3D Engine. Unity3D, which is particularly suitable for smaller or mid-sized development studios, seamlessly integrates visual simulation with interactive functionalities [40]. The office building scene was meticulously designed to immerse users in a typical office environment, providing insights into a standard workday involving elevator usage. The scene authentically reproduces details, such as elevator buttons, and is developed in alignment with vertical transportation theory, which employs identical input parameters and faithfully represents the associated mathematical calculations (see Fig. 12). The sole restriction we faced was the necessity to uphold the graphical elements within the capabilities easily renderable by standard cell phones. Selecting the optimal frame rate for a 3D game developed in Unity for Android devices requires balancing between visual quality and performance. During app testing, we opted for the “fast” option after evaluating all seven available quality levels, which included fastest, fast, simple, good, beautiful, and fantastic. We opted for Unity’s default option of 30 frames per second (FPS). Higher FPS is essential in scenarios to prevent nausea during prolonged usage or when there are rapid movements in simulations, yet it brings drawbacks such as battery drainage. Each frame is allocated a time budget corresponding to the target FPS. An application targeting 30 FPS consistently completes each frame in under 33.33 milliseconds (1000 ms / 30 FPS). Leaving approximately 35% of frame idle time is typically recommended to mitigate device thermal issues during extended play times. A typical frame budget is approximately 22 ms per frame $(1000 \text{ ms} / 30) * 0.65 = 21.66 \text{ ms}$. Achieving 60 fps on mobile necessitates a target frame time of 10.83 ms, which is challenging on many mobile devices and would drain the battery twice as fast compared to targeting 30 fps. Therefore, most mobile games opt to target 30 fps instead of 60 for these reasons.

In terms of resolution and presentation, in resolution scaling mode we opted for fixed dots per inch (DPI). So, the application's resolution, or target DPI, determines how Unity adjusts the resolution if the device's native screen DPI exceeds this value. Unity calculates the scaling using $\min(\text{target DPI} * \text{factor} / \text{screen DPI}, 1)$, where factor represents the resolution scaling fixed DPI factor from the quality settings.

We utilized Unity's Universal Render Pipeline (URP), a prebuilt scriptable render pipeline that offers workflows for developers to create optimized graphics across various platforms, from mobile to high-end consoles and PCs. URP introduces the render graph system, which leverages the scriptable render pipeline API to enhance the customization and maintenance of the render pipeline. It supports deployment across more than 17 platforms, including VR headsets, mobile devices, high-end consoles, and desktop machines. The render graph system in URP reduces URP's memory footprint and improves memory management efficiency. It employs techniques such as reducing CPU rendering workload, GPU occlusion culling, and mipmap streaming. In the testing phase we made sure that the apps interface and simulation are fixed in the horizontal orientation and are rendered smoothly. The mobile resolution tested was in the range of five common screen sizes between $320 \times 480 - 1440 \times 3200$. We performed the graphical user interface functionality for menus, dropdown, navigation buttons and other existing elements. It was important to test the app in different versions of the operating system for compatibility issues. Our app did not concern accessibility modes, browser optimality, or fast internet speed so we did not test for them. Our focus is on training and educational functionality, as well as collecting results. To minimize potential bias in our experiments, we deliberately avoided complex architectural and functional designs that could introduce additional variables requiring evaluation.

We used the level of detail groups, occlusion culling or selectively object rendering, general lights without shadows, and texture and material optimization. Additionally, we utilized material instead of objects to reduce the polygon count on every frame, particularly for objects further from the camera. Optimizing the rendering of the scene implied the use of unity's profiler. Unity's profiler is a tool used to gather performance information about applications, testing how they perform on the intended release platform. It collects and displays data on CPU usage, memory consumption, rendering performance, and audio processing. This tool is invaluable for pinpointing bottlenecks or areas that need performance enhancements. The application underwent testing on physical cell phones and various configurations in emulators.

Due to the absence of Haptic VR devices and the pre-downloaded nature of the application, there were no network delays as all simulations occur offline in a form of real-time rendering and no information is sent until all simulations are finished. The input menu at the beginning

eliminates distractions during the simulation. After completing all simulations, the application sends the results, ensuring there are no delays due to network connections that could compromise the quality of the experience. This involved employing HTML post queries to transmit the test feedback results at the conclusion of the experiment. The test feedback, weighing less than 100kb and formatted in JSON, was designed to minimize disruption to the experiment flow. To ensure internal validity, we adopted a minimalist design approach in terms of the testbed. The technical architecture illustrates the design elements, where the mobile application provides an interactive user interface for inputting values related to the simulation's parameters. Once the values are entered, the simulation is presented to the user. After each simulation, the evaluation and feedback module generate reports. This process is repeated as many times as the user deems necessary during a training session. All evaluations are saved locally and transmitted to the server once the training session is complete. Subsequently, all data is communicated to the server, where the information from all users is stored, as outlined in the data acquisition and storage process. Once the data is aggregated, researchers can access it for further analysis (see Fig. 13).

FIGURE 12. Building scene.

C. CRITICAL THINKING EVALUATION

An effective tool for evaluating CT is to accurately predict real-world behavior. The Hybrid Critical Thinking Assessment (HCTA) test specifically anticipates adults' actions in their daily lives, focusing on what they claim to do. The test comprises five dimensions constituting CT skills: "verbal reasoning", "argument analysis", "thinking as hypothesis testing", "likelihood and uncertainty", and "decision-making and problem-solving". The test structure involved 20 daily scenarios, each generating a constructed response from which the best response was selected. This approach provides distinct measures of recall and recognition memory [41], [42].

CT assessments can be approached through two distinct methods: one involving multiple-choice selections with

FIGURE 13. Technical architecture.

closed answers and the other centered around open-ended questions. The former typically exhibits acceptable statistical validity, but is limited to predetermined aspects, posing challenges for repetition. In contrast, open-ended questions, while displaying limited reliability, offer greater adaptability to specific needs and ease of repetition. HCTA combines both approaches, incorporating multiple choice and open-ended questions [28]. Consequently, this study adopted an HCTA.

In every dimension, the constructed response format assesses “free recall,” requiring test-takers to consciously search and select relevant knowledge and skills from their memory to form an answer. These response items require higher-level cognitive processing. Additionally, the forced-choice items gauge “recognition memory,” demanding that test-takers identify the appropriate response from a provided list of alternatives. In HCTA, there is a correlation between dimensions, weight, and each type of question (see Fig. 14). HCTA has two test versions: standard and short. The former includes two question types (constructed response and forced choice), with a Cronbach’s α reliability of 0.88. The latter comprised only forced-choice questions, with Cronbach’s α reliability of 0.77. A minimum sample size of 60 was required to achieve these reliability measures [41].

Each dimension comprises four scenarios, and the overall score is determined by both types of questions (constructed and forced-choice responses). However, an equal number of scenarios were assigned to each CT category, with certain categories carrying more points than the others. In each scenario, the respondents were required to answer an open-ended question, followed by a forced-choice question. Ultimately, the total score is equally influenced by both the constructed responses and forced-choice questions.

FIGURE 14. CT dimension weights.

Within the three dimensions of HCTA, two focus on language and logical constructs that are not significantly relevant to the visual and experiential aspects of CT. The “likelihood and uncertainty dimension” is crucial in unconstrained situations, but in elevator traffic training, which is a controlled environment, uncertainty’s role in decision-making is not substantial. Evaluating this dimension makes more sense when performed after each simulation, not after training, so it was excluded from the assessment. Specifically, according to the manual, the verbal reasoning dimension assesses “the skills needed to comprehend and defend against persuasive techniques embedded in everyday language (also known as natural language).” The argument analysis dimension, as defined in the manual, relates to “the skills of identifying conclusions, rating the quality of reasons, and determining the overall strength of an argument that are essential in understanding complex and extended arguments.” Finally, the dimension Using Likelihood and Uncertainty, as shown in the manual, relates to “the correct use of probability and likelihood in almost every decision” [41].

TABLE 4. Adaptation of dimension weights for the CT test.

CT dimension	Weight	Open-ended question	Forced choice question
Decision making and problem-solving	60%	4	4
Thinking as hypothesis testing	40%	4	4

FIGURE 15. Relation between collected information and CT.

Considering that only two scenarios evaluating the CT of engineers in the vertical transport industry are relevant, we adopt only the “decision-making and problem-solving” and “thinking as hypothesis testing” dimensions from the HCTA (see Table 4 and Fig. 15). Each dimension comprised four scenarios, each featuring both open-ended and closed questions, resulting in a total of 16 questions in the test, with eight questions for each type. Open-ended and closed questions carry equal weights in grading, although the total sum of the values contributes differently to each dimension.

For measuring two dimensions “decision making and problem-solving” and “thinking as hypothesis testing.” Each question type corresponds to one of the following variables: free recall or recognition memory. Free recall is a memory task in which participants attempt to remember previously studied information in any order. Recognition memory refers to the ability to identify a familiar stimulus or situation that has been encountered previously.

The comparative analysis between VR training and the conventional methodology involves assessing engineers’ performance based on the CT criteria. A user survey gauges the level of a “compelling experience” to validate whether users perceived any differences in space, time, emotions, or health, enhancing the viability of the experiment.

For reference, compelling experience was measured through two types of outputs: qualitative data from questions in the final test and quantitative data directly from the software report. Qualitative questions in the final test aim to gauge the acceptance of digital transformation through inquiries such as “What is the perception of the helpfulness of VR in training?” or ‘Would you use VR for learning again?’ Similarly, quantitative questions measured the frequency of user immersion in VR software with different scenarios and the duration of each immersion.

The evaluation of the impact of VR digital transformation on training engineers primarily revolves around enhancing CT parameters. Economic analysis adds another dimension to the comparison. However, additional factors such as compelling experience and economic viability were considered as reference points. We defined the usability of VR as a digital transformation tool related to CT enhancement, compelling experience, and economic viability, and measured the performance of each by different testing methods directly in the VR application or with a final test (see Fig. 16).

FIGURE 16. Different factors measure the performance of the VR digital transformation to the conventional engineers’ training.

The variables and weights related to CT enhancement based on HCTA, specifically the Halpern model, are summarized in the following formula [41]:

PTK: Preliminary test about knowledge of the subject matter

E-CT: CT enhancement

DM1: Decision-making and problem-solving dimension.

DM1-FRC: Free recall by multiple-choice questions.

DM1-RM: Recognition memory by open-ended questions.

DM2: Thinking as hypothesis testing dimension.

DM2-FRC: Free recall by multiple-choice questions.

DM2-RM: Recognition memory by open-ended questions.

$$E - CT = 0.6 * (0.5 * FRC + 0.5 * RM)_{DM1} + 0.4 * (0.5 * FRC + 0.5 * RM)_{DM2}$$

This assessment contrasts the influence of conventional training and VR technology on two dimensions associated with

CT: decision-making and problem-solving and thinking as hypothesis testing in engineering students. The CT process enhancement outlined in Table 5 reflects the existing approach adopted by Latin American companies in the elevator industry. An expert typically visits each subsidiary company in different countries to conduct enhancement activities with a specific focus on CT skills in vertical transportation traffic.

TABLE 5. Enhancement of CT process.

Step		Conventional	VR
1	Learning process	- Explanation by expert - Explanation by video - Study by self	
2	Learning by doing	- Use of mathematical software - Monitoring and accompaniment of an expert	- Use of VR software
3	Result	Enhancement of CT skill	

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A preliminary test on knowledge of the subject matter or PKE defines the baseline knowledge of subjects about the subject matter (see Fig. 17). Considering their novice status in this subject, the knowledge level was deemed acceptable, with over 90% of participants noting that they had not been exposed to the term “traffic of vertical transportation.”

FIGURE 17. Result of the preliminary test (the maximum score X is 5).

We can observe in training stages, both groups between stages 0 and 2 receive instructions, a preliminary test, and a video training session. In stage 3, they received corresponding training in conventional or VR-based training. Finally, both groups were tested using CT (see Table 6).

Sample A pertains to the survey conducted with the conventional training group, while Sample B is connected to the investigation of VR training (see Tables 7 and 8). Both tested

samples exhibited a comparable understanding of vertical transportation traffic.

TABLE 6. Training stages.

Stage	Conventional training		VR-based training systems	
	Topic	Time	Topic	Time
Stage 0	Instructions	5 min	Instructions	5 min
Stage 1 (Calibration)	Preliminary test	10 min	Preliminary test	10 min
Stage 2 (Learning process)	Video	10 min	Video	10 min
Stage 3 (Learning by doing)	Instructions Software	5 min 10 min	Instructions VR Software	5 min 10 min
Stage 3 (Final test)	CT test	20 min	CT test	20 min
	Total time	60 min	Total time	60 min

TABLE 7. CT scores for Sample A.

Sample type		Sample A				
		E-CT	DM1		DM2	
			FRC	RM	FRC	RM
Max	Scores	6.8	4.0	4.0	4.0	3.00
	%	86%	100%	100%	100%	75%
Min	Scores	4.3	1.8	1.9	0.5	1.00
	%	53%	22%	24%	6%	13%
Mean	Scores	5.4	3.1	3.2	2.4	2.13
	%	68%	39%	40%	30%	27%
$X \geq 7$		0	Total FRC average: 39% Total RM average 29%			
$6 \leq X < 7$		30				
$5 \leq X < 6$		94				
$3 \leq X < 5$		53				
$X < 3$		0				

Post-training, assessing the improvement in CT and adaptation of the HCTA for each group yielded results above the average. Although both groups demonstrated commendable outcomes (see Tables 7 and 8), it is discernible that Sample B, who was trained with VR, achieved superior results. This distinction is evident in the fact that a greater percentage of participants in Sample B scored within the range of 6 to 7 out of 7 compared to Sample A, which predominantly obtained scores within the range of 5 to 6 out of 7 (see Fig. 18).

The subsequent data pertains to the satisfaction level derived from the VR experience, serving as a gauge to identify the extent of engagement generated by VR training. The pie chart labeled “VR experience rating” provides an evaluation of VR designed to assess the overall satisfaction with the product (see Fig. 19). Likewise, the pie chart labeled “VR as learning tool rating” measures whether participants

TABLE 8. CT scores for Sample B.

Sample type		Sample B				
		E-CT	DM1		DM2	
			FRC	RM	FRC	RM
Max	Scores	7.9	4.00	3.90	4.00	4.00
	%	99%	100%	98%	100%	100%
Min	Scores	4.9	2.25	2.00	2.00	1.00
	%	61%	56%	50%	50%	25%
Average	Scores	6.6	3.33	3.31	3.33	3.28
	%	83%	83%	83%	83%	82%
$X \geq 7$		53	Total FRC average: 83% Total RM average 83%			
$6 \leq X < 7$		83				
$5 \leq X < 6$		35				
$3 \leq X < 5$		6				
$X < 3$		0				

perceive the VR experience as beneficial for technical training. Both measures employed a scale ranging from 1 to 5, where 5 signifies the highest rating and 1 denotes the lowest rating. Notably, 93% of trainees expressed an inclination toward using VR technology to learn about various subjects (see Fig. 20).

FIGURE 18. Result of Halpern critical thinking test (the maximum score X is 7).

FIGURE 19. Compelling experience.

The server side, created using node.js, documented the information transmitted by the VR software Unity 3D [43],

FIGURE 20. VR as a learning tool.

[44]. The compiled data indicated that, on average, each simulation extended for approximately 3 min. Across 176 samples, the server stored supplementary details for each simulated scenario, serving both as a backup and for potential training an AI-based application in the future.

One of the key benefits offered by VR in industrial training is its ability to explore hazardous or challenging spaces without exposing trainees to risks. Additionally, there are economic advantages, including cost reduction in transportation, renting, and purchasing spaces [45]. We developed a VR solution aimed at eliminating the expenses associated with travel by experts or trainees or the creation of physical labs. Our solution incorporates various scenarios, significantly reducing the cost of the designed HMDs. We manufactured 80 reusable HMDs that are compact, easily transportable, and can be assembled effortlessly at the trainee’s location. Recreating them is even more cost-effective than sending them over long distances. While the market HMD prices range from \$15 US to \$700 US, our solution comes at a cost of approximately \$4 US. Furthermore, altering the training parameters poses no risks or dangers, allowing for a wide range of realistic training scenarios. This amplifies the risk-free aspect of the return on investment, encouraging experimentation with VR training and challenging the design paradigms where cost was a predominant barrier to implementation [32].

Previous research lacks conclusive evidence regarding the enhancement of CT skills in industry engineers’ VR training. Previous research lacks conclusive evidence regarding the enhancement of CT skills in industry engineers’ VR training [45]. The empirical investigation involving both VR-based and traditional trainees revealed that while they addressed technical elevator aspects in response to open-ended questions, VR trainees also incorporated details related to the influence of physical space and time. Notably, a comparison of the results between VR-based and traditional training demonstrated a 54% increase in the industry engineers’ CT recognition memory score. Our hybrid assessment of CT skills using open-ended questions provides confidence in minimizing the likelihood of systematic errors when relying solely on multiple-choice questions for skill evaluation.

The findings affirm that retention rates in 'learning by doing' approaches surpass those of traditional audio-visual methods [14]. Previous research suggests that CT, as a skill, empowers individuals to generate new knowledge and solve everyday problems [28]. The results of the current study clearly demonstrate that immersive experiences enhance CT skills by an average of 15% compared to conventional training. The VR-based approach stimulates trainees to cultivate curiosity in decision-making scenarios, encouraging them to explore alternative approaches and to consider the consequences of their decisions. The controlled movement of the field of view and the longer design of the HMDs, alongside the decisions on using less glossy material design, facilitated postponing or occurrences of VR sickness. The inclination to participate in the experience serves as evidence of this. This is an improvement in the experience of VR training that improves the sensations reported in previous research [34], [35], [36].

The responses to open-ended questions, when coupled with the quality of experience, revealed that trainees value personalized training tailored to their profiles. The data collected after each training iteration, combined with historical data, allows for automatic data analysis and the development of optimized solutions as the training progresses. The synergistic application of AI and on-demand cloud computing has the potential to enhance this process substantially. The examination of written responses suggests that interaction with the environment, particularly concerning space and time, promotes motivation and associative memory, and enhances cognitive learning. Trainees expressed that additional conditions or parameters could contribute to a better learning experience, including team collaboration, reward systems (such as badge recognition), competition, flexibility to repeat training at preferred hours, and availability of indefinite trials with varying difficulty levels. The utilization of VR software proved intuitive and natural, allowing participants to firsthand experience the cognitive consequences of their decisions. This adds a new dimension of knowledge beyond the theoretical and mathematical understanding of each change introduced into the environment.

Furthermore, the literature review indicates the long-term advantages of the initial investment in VR-based systems compared to traditional training. These benefits encompass the reuse and automation of business processes, the seamless integration of the training process into the company's technological infrastructure, and alignment with digital transformation strategies. Cloud-based development facilitates economies of scale in training quantity, information and knowledge management, and transparency in the training process for top level managers. The advantages of VR-based experiential training, involving a sense of presence in both the environment and perception of time and space, could be extrapolated to simulation-based education. In simulation-based scenarios, trainees decide the parameters, run simulations, and observe their consequences. However, the results of this study indicate that the integration of senses with

the VR training environment significantly enhances learning outcomes, providing immersive properties that traditional simulations lack. Additionally, centralized data collection allows for monitoring the process and tracking long-term improvements in the training process within an international company, which has numerous branches worldwide.

Literature often emphasizes the application of AR to industrial digital solutions. However, the experiment conducted in this study identified several factors that distinguish VR from AR. In VR, there is flexibility in designing an environment without limitations on the hypothetical size or properties of the domain. However, AR relies on the camera and is partially constrained by the actual location information. VR creates entirely imaginary computer-based spaces, thus enabling scalable and remote training. In contrast, AR depends on images from the environment, limiting accessibility for trainees located offsite and incurring additional costs, thus making scalability less straightforward. VR offers unlimited imaginary or exaggerated alternatives, whereas AR depends on the structure of the location. In conclusion, it is conceivable that specific priorities and the nature of the task may dictate the scenarios in which either AR or VR is a more suitable solution.

In educational and social sciences, experiments are valued for their strong internal validity. Randomly assigning treatment conditions ensures that the estimated treatment effect is causal. However, a challenge arises in generalizing findings from the experiment to a larger population. Ideal statistical practice for this requires two steps: first, randomly selecting the experimental sample from a defined population, and second, randomly assigning units in the sample to treatment conditions. In this particular case, we randomly selected samples from a diverse pool of engineering students and industry practitioners. We then assigned both the traditional and virtual reality (VR) methodologies to them in a wholly randomized manner. We designed the minimal software and the hardware by applying methods that assure validity of results. The experiment instructions required a room with adequate internet access, sufficient lighting, no obstacles, and silence. Additionally, participants were instructed to calibrate the VR application and ensure proper configuration of the HMDs. The experiment design excludes disruptive elements such as haptic devices or interactions during the presentation of the simulation. This ensures that critical thinking indicators are accurately measured while minimizing the influence of other factors. The application is pre-downloaded and optimized for rendering objects. Internet communication occurs only after all experiments are completed and involves transmitting a minimal amount of data, enhancing the overall user experience.

Experiential learning leverages haptic devices and continuous interaction with the environment to integrate various associations in the brain, potentially enhancing CT. This approach proves beneficial in fields such as healthcare, medicine, nursing, chemistry lab training, and military decisions pertaining to close combat, and it may also influence

memory retention. However, in our experiment, we deliberately omitted these elements to uphold the internal and external validity of our results concerning CT training.

In diverse domains, scenarios that involve observing decision outcomes and facing novel situations can significantly enhance decision-making skills. The approach delineated in this research holds promise for such contexts. As mentioned in the related work section, in military settings, instances may include tasks undertaken by red teams, such as providing operational support, aiding in planning and decision-making, critically reviewing existing plans, and offering intelligence support by emulating threats to facilitate the learning process. In clinical settings, examples encompass ill-defined medical emergencies, wherein medical personnel must exercise sound judgment to navigate clinical situations and effectively resolve clinical challenges. We are confronted with a myriad of novel challenges concerning the integration of datasets, which interconnect diverse realms through the utilization of big data. These challenges encompass environmental issues, dilemmas pertaining to weapons of mass destruction, political controversies surrounding resource allocation, mental health challenges, escalating violence, pandemic scenarios, and an aging population. These global challenges place immense strain on resources and pose existential threats to life on Earth. Addressing these urgent issues effectively necessitates the expertise of well-educated and critically thinking individuals. VR simulations can provide a platform for honing critical thinking and reasoning skills, facilitating more informed decision-making processes in response to these complex situations. In our study, we demonstrated that software training integrating critical thinking (CT) skills leads to improved decision-making capabilities in scenarios mirroring real-world situations.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The industry actively seeks market adaptability and sustainability, particularly during crises, necessitating waste reduction and process optimization. Digital technology is key, enabling effective digital transformation through requirement identification, parameter measurement, gap description, stakeholder-inclusive solution design, and integrated change implementation. To thrive and respond to challenges like Covid-19, companies must swiftly adopt technology for a competitive edge. This urgency is heightened in emerging countries, where physical displacement costs drive inequality, prompting remote work.

Our research focuses on developing a VR methodology for teaching and assessing critical thinking skills among engineers, addressing complex scenarios. This innovative approach integrates critical thinking into VR software design, emphasizing decision-making in uncertain situations. Industries benefiting from this approach include healthcare, engineering, and the military, where traditional training falls short. For example, in vertical transportation engineering, critical thinking is crucial for optimizing building designs. Delays in decision-making impact customer service,

highlighting the need for efficient training methods. Our methodology aims to address these challenges by providing swift and reliable decision-making skills training, replacing costly and inadequate traditional methods.

In terms of the training budget, VR-based training systems offer significant advantages over conventional methods, even when factoring in the costs of VR HMDs. Once a company invests in this solution, the long-term benefits become apparent. For example, eliminating travel expenses reduces overall costs. The incorporation of low-cost analytics enables data acquisition, and the delivery of personalized training based on historical data tailored to the specific needs of engineers. Automated analytics and training align with the broader digital transformation strategies of a company.

Our current methodology is constrained to training without incorporating novel artificial intelligence approaches. Future research should focus on the implementation of personalized and customized techniques that utilize generative models in multimodal machine learning. This approach can enhance individual experience and tailor training to specific needs, thereby enhancing inclusion. Additionally, the integration of reinforcement learning has the potential to enhance learning scenarios and training methodologies, and ultimately expedite solution development. Future research has the potential to enhance the value by validating the results across various industries and incorporating additional sample types to confirm its generalizability to diverse domains. Additionally, future research could explore aspects related to skill retention and memory within the context of learning.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank Prof. Luis Eduardo Díaz Barrera of Sabana University for his biosecurity suggestions regarding the reusability of HMDs. They also applied free ChatGPT 3.5 for English proofing their manuscript and they are grateful for this service.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Zahidi, V. Ratcheva, G. Hingel, and S. Brown, "The future of jobs report 2020," World Econ. Forum, Cologny, Switzerland, Tech. Rep. 2020-2025, 2020.
- [2] J. Häkkinen, A. Colley, J. Väyrynen, and A.-J. Yliharju, "Introducing virtual reality technologies to design education," *Seminar. Net*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 1–12, Jun. 2018, doi: [10.7577/seminar.2584](https://doi.org/10.7577/seminar.2584).
- [3] IDC Corporate. (2023). *AR & VR Headsets Market Share*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.idc.com/promo/arvr>
- [4] P. Zawadzki, K. Zywicki, P. Bun, and F. Górski, "Employee training in an intelligent factory using virtual reality," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 135110–135117, 2020, doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3010439](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3010439).
- [5] W. de Paula Ferreira, F. Armellini, and L. De Santa-Eulalia, "Simulation in Industry 4.0: A state-of-the-art review," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 149, Nov. 2020, Art. no. 106868, doi: [10.1016/j.cie.2020.106868](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2020.106868).
- [6] M. Akdere and T. Egan, "Transformational leadership and human resource development: Linking employee learning, job satisfaction, and organizational performance," *Hum. Resource Develop. Quart.*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 393–421, Dec. 2020, doi: [10.1002/hrdq.21404](https://doi.org/10.1002/hrdq.21404).
- [7] A. Bryman, "Integrating quantitative and qualitative research: How is it done?" *Qualitative Res.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 97–113, Feb. 2006, doi: [10.1177/1468794106058877](https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794106058877).
- [8] L. A. Burke and H. M. Hutchins, "Training transfer: An integrative literature review," *Hum. Resource Develop. Rev.*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 263–296, Sep. 2007, doi: [10.1177/1534484307303035](https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484307303035).

- [9] R. Grossman and E. Salas, "The transfer of training: What really matters," *Int. J. Training Develop.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 103–120, Jun. 2011, doi: [10.1111/j.1468-2419.2011.00373.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2419.2011.00373.x).
- [10] C. Bossard, G. Kermarrec, C. Buche, and J. Tisseau, "Transfer of learning in virtual environments: A new challenge?" *Virtual Reality*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 151–161, Sep. 2008, doi: [10.1007/s10055-008-0093-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-008-0093-y).
- [11] S. C. Michalski, A. Szpak, D. Saredakis, T. J. Ross, M. Billingham, and T. Loetscher, "Getting your game on: Using virtual reality to improve real table tennis skills," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 14, no. 9, Sep. 2019, Art. no. e0222351, doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0222351](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0222351).
- [12] V. B. Issurin, "Training transfer: Scientific background and insights for practical application," *Sports Med.*, vol. 43, no. 8, pp. 675–694, Aug. 2013, doi: [10.1007/s40279-013-0049-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-013-0049-6).
- [13] C. Våpenstad, E. F. Hofstad, L. E. Bø, E. Kuhry, G. Johnsen, R. Mårvik, T. Langø, and T. N. Hernes, "Lack of transfer of skills after virtual reality simulator training with haptic feedback," *Minimally Invasive Therapy Allied Technol.*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 346–354, Nov. 2017, doi: [10.1080/13645706.2017.1319866](https://doi.org/10.1080/13645706.2017.1319866).
- [14] H. Ebbesen and C. Machholdt, "Digital reality changes everything," Deloitte Digit., London, U.K., Tech. Rep., 2019.
- [15] A. Y. Kolb and D. A. Kolb, "Experiential learning theory as a guide for experiential educators in higher education," *Experiential Learn. Teaching Higher Educ.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 7–44, Sep. 2022, doi: [10.46787/elthe.v1i1.3362](https://doi.org/10.46787/elthe.v1i1.3362).
- [16] B. A. Mukhalalati and A. Taylor, "Adult learning theories in context: A quick guide for healthcare professional educators," *J. Med. Educ. Curricular Develop.*, vol. 6, Apr. 2019, Art. no. 238212051984033, doi: [10.1177/2382120519840332](https://doi.org/10.1177/2382120519840332).
- [17] D. A. Kolb, "Experiential learning in training and organization," in *Experiential Learning: Experience as the Source of Learning and Development*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ, USA: Pearson, 2015, pp. 8–11.
- [18] M. Kaur and R. Mahajan, "Inculcating critical thinking skills in medical students: Ways and means," *Int. J. Appl. Basic Med. Res.*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 57–58, 2023, doi: [10.4103/ijabmr.ijabmr_214_23](https://doi.org/10.4103/ijabmr.ijabmr_214_23).
- [19] S. C. Fischer, V. A. Spiker, and S. L. Riedel, *Critical Thinking Training for Army Officers Vol II: A Model of Critical Thinking*. Santa Barbara, CA, USA: Anacapa Sciences, 2009.
- [20] D. F. Halpern, *Critical Thinking Across the Curriculum*. New York, NY, USA: Taylor Francis, 2013, doi: [10.4324/9781315805719](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315805719).
- [21] A. Ahern, C. Dominguez, C. McNally, J. J. O'Sullivan, and D. Pedrosa, "A literature review of critical thinking in engineering education," *Stud. Higher Educ.*, vol. 44, no. 5, pp. 816–828, May 2019, doi: [10.1080/03075079.2019.1586325](https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2019.1586325).
- [22] H. W. J. Rittel and M. M. Webber, "Dilemmas in a general theory of planning," *Policy Sci.*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 155–169, Jun. 1973.
- [23] J. Lönngren and M. Svanström, "Assessing the 'wicked sustainability problem'—Literacy in engineering education," in *Proc. ASEE Annu. Conf. Expo.*, 2015, pp. 26.255.1–26.255.13, doi: [10.18260/p.23585](https://doi.org/10.18260/p.23585).
- [24] D. Jonassen, J. Strobel, and C. B. Lee, "Everyday problem solving in engineering: Lessons for engineering educators," *J. Eng. Educ.*, vol. 95, no. 2, pp. 139–151, Apr. 2006, doi: [10.1002/j.2168-9830.2006.tb00885.x](https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2006.tb00885.x).
- [25] *Outcomes and Assessment Handbook*, Clovis Community College, Clovis, CA, USA, 2019.
- [26] D. Adair and M. Jaeger, "Incorporating critical thinking into an engineering undergraduate learning environment," *Int. J. Higher Educ.*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 23–39, Jan. 2016, doi: [10.5430/ijhe.v5n2p23](https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v5n2p23).
- [27] ABET. (Sep. 14, 2020). *Criteria for Accrediting Engineering Programs, 2019–2020*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.abet.org/accreditation/accreditation-criteria/criteria-for-accrediting-engineering-programs-2019-2020/>
- [28] C. Ossa, M. Palma, N. Lagos, I. Quintana, and C. Diaz, "Analysis of critical thinking measurement instruments," *Ciencias Psicológicas*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 19–28, 2017, doi: [10.22235/cp.v11i2.1343](https://doi.org/10.22235/cp.v11i2.1343).
- [29] K. Berntsen, R. C. Palacios, and E. Herranz, "Virtual reality and its uses: A systematic literature review," in *Proc. 4th Int. Conf. Technolog. Ecosyst. Enhancing Multiculturality*. New York, NY, USA: ACM, Nov. 2016, pp. 435–439, doi: [10.1145/3012430.3012553](https://doi.org/10.1145/3012430.3012553).
- [30] S. A. Karre, N. Mathur, and Y. R. Reddy, "Usability evaluation of VR products in industry: A systematic literature review," in *Proc. 34th ACM/SIGAPP Symp. Appl. Comput.*, vol. 2, New York, NY, USA, Apr. 2019, pp. 1845–1851, doi: [10.1145/3297280.3297462](https://doi.org/10.1145/3297280.3297462).
- [31] L. Freina and M. Ott, "A literature review on immersive virtual reality in education: State of the art and perspectives," in *Proc. Int. Sci. Conf. eLearn. Softw. Educ.*, Apr. 2015, vol. 1, no. 133, pp. 1–8, doi: [10.12753/2066-026x-15-020](https://doi.org/10.12753/2066-026x-15-020). [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280566372_A_Literature_Review_on_Immersive_Virtual_Reality_in_Education_State_Of_The_Art_and_Perspectives
- [32] C. Laurell, C. Sandström, A. Berthold, and D. Larsson, "Exploring barriers to adoption of virtual reality through social media analytics and machine learning—An assessment of technology, network, price and trialability," *J. Bus. Res.*, vol. 100, pp. 469–474, Jul. 2019, doi: [10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.01.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.01.017).
- [33] Statista. (Nov. 15, 2023). *Virtual Reality (VR) Headset Average Price Worldwide From 2018 to 2028*. Accessed: Dec. 12, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.statista.com/forecasts/1338351/vr-headset-average-price-worldwide>
- [34] E. Chang, H. T. Kim, and B. Yoo, "Virtual reality sickness: A review of causes and measurements," *Int. J. Hum.-Comput. Interact.*, vol. 36, no. 17, pp. 1658–1682, Oct. 2020, doi: [10.1080/10447318.2020.1778351](https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2020.1778351).
- [35] D. Saredakis, A. Szpak, B. Birkhead, H. A. D. Keage, A. Rizzo, and T. Loetscher, "Factors associated with virtual reality sickness in head-mounted displays: A systematic review and meta-analysis," *Frontiers Hum. Neurosci.*, vol. 14, p. 96, Mar. 2020, doi: [10.3389/fnhum.2020.00096](https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2020.00096).
- [36] J. Won and Y. S. Kim, "A new approach for reducing virtual reality sickness in real time: Design and validation study," *JMIR Serious Games*, vol. 10, no. 3, Sep. 2022, Art. no. e36397, doi: [10.2196/36397](https://doi.org/10.2196/36397).
- [37] J. vom Brocke, A. Hevner, and A. Maedche, "Introduction to design science research," in *Design Science Research. Cases*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2020, pp. 1–13, doi: [10.1007/978-3-030-46781-4_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-46781-4_1).
- [38] D. Metzger, C. Niemöller, B. Wingert, T. Schultze, M. Bues, and O. Thomas, "How machines are serviced—Design of a virtual reality-based training system for technical customer services," in *Proc. 13th Int. Conf. Wirtschaftsinformatik*, St. Gallen, Switzerland, 2017, pp. 1–15.
- [39] *Google Cardboard*. Accessed: Nov. 22, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arvr.google.com/cardboard/>
- [40] J. Ikhsan, K. H. Sugiyarto, and T. N. Astuti, "Fostering student's critical thinking through a virtual reality laboratory," *Int. J. Interact. Mobile Technol.*, vol. 14, no. 8, pp. 183–195, May 2020, doi: [10.3991/ijim.v14i08.13069](https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v14i08.13069).
- [41] D. F. Halpern, "Halpern critical thinking assessment MANUAL," Schufried, Mödling, Austria, Tech. Rep., 2016.
- [42] D. F. Halpern, *Thought and Knowledge: An Introduction to Critical Thinking*. New York, NY, USA: Psychology Press, 2014.
- [43] Unity Technol. *Unity Real-Time Development Platform | 3D, 2D, VR & AR Engine*. Accessed: Nov. 22, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://unity.com/>
- [44] OpenJS Found. *Node.js*. Accessed: Nov. 22, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://nodejs.org/en/>
- [45] M. S. Fairuz and A. Z. Nasir, "Virtual reality in manufacturing," Tech. Rep., 2014. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228875829_Virtual_Reality_in_Manufacturing

YAVAR JARRAH-NEZHAD received the bachelor's and master's degrees in IT from Moscow State University, focusing on big data analysis, and the Ph.D. degree in economics. He is currently an Associate Professor with Escuela Colombiana de Ingeniería Julio Garavito. He has more than ten years of international experience in the public and private sectors, particularly in Colombia with entities, such as Colombian Health Ministry, the Ministry of Information and Communications Technologies, and universities, such as Universidad de La Sabana, Universidad El Bosque, Universidad del Rosario, and the Universidad Católica de El Salvador. His research interests include the application of artificial intelligence in data science, cloud computing, big data, and strategic management integrating Industry 4.0 and 5.0 technologies.

LUIS A. PAIPA-GALEANO received the degree in agro-industrial production engineering, the master's degree in education, and the Ph.D. degree in industrial engineering from the University of Navarra. He is a Distinguished Professor of Quality Management at the Faculty of Engineering, Universidad de La Sabana. He combines technical expertise with a deep understanding of educational methodologies. His research centers on the sustainability and practical integration of the continuous improvement philosophy within organizational contexts, contributing to the advancement of sustainable business practices, and operational excellence.

YAMID DELGHANS-JACOME received the M.Eng. degree in management from Universidad de La Sabana. He is currently a Mechanical Engineer. He is also a Vertical Transportation Expert in the Elevator Industry. His research interests include sustainability, business management, and Industry 5.0.

CÉSAR A. BERNAL-TORRES received the master's degree in education and the Ph.D. degree in business administration. He is currently a Professor with the Research and Innovation Seminar, International School of Economic and Administrative Sciences, Universidad de La Sabana. He is also an Economist and Psychologist. His research interests include business innovation, sustainability, and knowledge management.

WILMER GARZÓN-ALFONSO received the double B.Sc. degree in computer engineering and mathematics from Escuela Colombiana de Ingeniería Julio Garavito, Colombia, the M.Sc. degree from the University of Puerto Rico at Mayagüez, and the Ph.D. degree from IMT Atlantique, France, and Escuela Colombiana de Ingeniería Julio Garavito. He is currently an Associate Professor of computer engineering with Escuela Colombiana de Ingeniería Julio Garavito. His research interests include data analytics, data mining, learning techniques, distributed learning, computing, and formal methods.

ANDRES FELIPE PÁEZ-CAICEDO is currently a Risk Analyst at the Financial Institutions that guarantee funds, Fogafin, Bogotá, Colombia. His research interests include optimization, machine learning, and simulation.

...